

Action of Grignard Reagents on Benzils

F. G. BADDAR*, A. F. M. FAHMY and NAWAL (MRS.) F ALY

Faculty of Science, A'in Shams University, Cairo, Egypt

Manuscript received 2 February 1973; accepted 27 June 1973

Benzils added one molecule of Grignard reagents to give the corresponding aroyldiaryl-carbinols (1-10). However, with excess of Grignard reagents, they gave pinacols (11-27). The structure of the carbinols (1-10) was established by i.r. and u.v. spectroscopy and by oxidation.

ROGER and McGregor¹ found that benzil reacts with *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-tolylmagnesium bromide to give the carbinols (1), (2), and (3), respectively. They concluded from the isolation of *o*-toluic acid instead of benzoic acid upon cleavage of (1) with alc. KOH, that rearrangement^{2,3(a)} occurred during the reaction of *o*-tolylmagnesium bromide with benzil. However, in a more recent publication⁴, it was reported that the rearrangement observed in the reaction of *o*-tolylmagnesium bromide with benzil may occur not during the addition of the Grignard reagent but during the alkaline cleavage step.

The study was extended in this investigation to *p*-methoxybenzil, *p*-chlorobenzil, *p*-anisil, and furil. It was found that these benzils add either one or two

molecules of Grignard reagents to give carbinols or pinacols, respectively.

Reactions leading to Addition of one Molecule of Grignard Reagents: When benzil (1 mol) was allowed to react with *o*-methoxyphenyl-magnesium bromide (1.5 mol), benzoyl *o*-methoxyphenyl phenyl carbinol (4) was obtained. Similarly, *p*-methoxybenzil reacted with phenylmagnesium bromide, benzylmagnesium chloride, *o*-methoxyphenyl-magnesium bromide (1.5 mol) under the same conditions to give (5), (6), and (7), respectively. Similarly, *p*-anisil reacted with phenyl- (1.5 mol), *o*-methoxyphenyl- (1.5 mol) magnesium bromide, and with benzylmagnesium chloride (3.5 mol) to give (8), (9), and (10), respectively (Scheme 1).

*Present Address: Dept. of Chemistry, Kuwait University, Kuwait

Ar	Ar'	Ar''	Ar	Ar'	Ar''
(1) Ph	Ph	C ₆ H ₄ Me(<i>o</i> -)	(11) Ph	Ph	Ph-CH ₂
(2) Ph	Ph	C ₆ H ₄ Me(<i>m</i> -)	(12) Ph	Ph	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>o</i> -)
(3) Ph	Ph	C ₆ H ₄ Me(<i>p</i> -)	(13) Ph	Ph	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)
(4) Ph	Ph	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>o</i> -)	(14) Ph	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	Ph
(5) Ph	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	Ph	(15) Ph	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	Ph-CH ₂
(6) Ph	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	(16) Ph	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>o</i> -)
(7) Ph	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>o</i> -)	(17) Ph	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)
(8) C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	Ph	(18) C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	Ph-CH ₂
(9) C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>o</i> -)	(19) C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>o</i> -)
(10) C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₅ -CH ₂	(20) C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)
			(21) Ph	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(<i>p</i> -)	Ph
			(22) Ph	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>o</i> -)
			(23) Ph	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(<i>p</i> -)	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)
			(24) C ₄ H ₄ O	C ₄ H ₄ O	Ph
			(25) C ₄ H ₄ O	C ₄ H ₄ O	Ph-CH ₂
			(26) C ₄ H ₄ O	C ₄ H ₄ O	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>o</i> -)
			(27) C ₄ H ₄ O	C ₄ H ₄ O	C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i> -)

The addition of one molecule of Grignard reagent may be due to the stability of the magnesium complex in the conformation (B) (Scheme 1), by coordination of the magnesium with the carbonyl oxygen. The addition of another molecule of Grignard reagent is inhibited by steric factors. However, *p*-chlorobenzil, and furil reacted with Grignard reagents to give pinacols (21–23) and (24–27), respectively, irrespective of the amount of Grignard reagent used.

Similarly, *p*-methoxyphenyl-magnesium bromide (excess), reacted with all benzils studied to give pinacols.

The structure of these products is established by a study of their i.r. spectra. Thus, the i.r. spectra of (4–10) show two bands in the regions, 1690–1660 cm⁻¹ (γ_{C-O} aromatic), and 3530–3380 cm⁻¹ (γ_{OH} single bridge)⁶ (Table 1). U.V. spectra of (4–10) revealed the presence of one band λ_{max} 276–289 nm, ϵ_{max} 15000–18700, which indicates that these compounds contain the same chromophoric system (Table 1).

Oxidative Cleavage of Aryl-diaryl Carbinols: When carbinols (5–10) in glacial acetic acid were heated⁶ with H₂O₂/HClO₄, a mixture of anisic acid, and the corresponding arylphenyl ketone was obtained. This revealed that no rearrangement occurred during reaction.

Reaction leading to Addition of two Molecules of Grignard Reagents: Benzil (1 mol) reacted with excess (6 mol) of benzyl-magnesium-chloride, *o*-, and *p*-methoxyphenyl-magnesium-bromide to give pinacols (11), (12), and (13) respectively. Similarly, *p*-methoxybenzil, anisil, *p*-chlorobenzil, and furil gave with excess of Grignard reagents the corresponding pinacols (14–27).

The structure of these compounds was inferred from (i) i.r. spectra which show ν_{OH} (single bridge), in the region 3500–3450 cm⁻¹ (Table 2), (ii) their analytical data.

These results indicate that most probably the reaction proceeds according to Scheme (1).

The formation of pinacols only by the interaction of benzil, *p*-methoxybenzil and *p*-anisil with *p*-methoxyphenylmagnesium-bromide, and by the interaction of *p*-chlorobenzil and furil with all Grignard reagents cited herein may be due to the strong nucleophilic character of *p*-anisylmagnesium-bromide in the former case, and to the high reactivity of the two carbonyl groups in the case of *p*-chlorobenzil and furil, that two molecules of the Grignard reagent add simultaneously, *i.e.*, while the complex resulting from the addition of the first molecule of Grignard reagent is still in the unchelated conformation (A)^{3b}

However, it was found that benzyl *p*-methoxybenzoyl phenyl carbinol (6) failed to react with excess of benzylmagnesium chloride. This shows that once the ketol is formed, it exists mainly single bridge complex (C); which is more sterically crowded, and less susceptible to further addition.

Experimental

I.r. (KBr disc) and u.v. spectra (in ethanol) were measured on a Unicam SP 1200 and Perkin-Elmer Spectracord model 4000A spectrophotometers, respectively.

Action of Grignard Reagents on Benzils: A solution of Grignard reagent (1.3–6 mol) in dry ether (10 ml) was added to solution of the benzil in dry ether (30 ml.). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hr, then worked up as usual. The product was crystallized from suitable solvent (Tables 1 and 2).

TABLE 1

Ar(CO) ₂ Ar	Mol. of Grignard reagent	Product	Yield %	M.p. °C	Found %		Formula	Required %		ν _{OH/cm-1}	ν _{C=O/cm-1}	λ _{max/nm} ε	
					C	H		C	H				
Ar = Ar' = Ph	1.5	4	76	162–164(E)	80.6	5.1	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₃	80.0	4.8	3500(s)	1680	—	—
Ar = Ph, Ar' = C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ p-	1.5	5	67	127–129(E)	78.6	5.7	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₃	79.2	5.7	3380(br)	1670	284	16900
	1.5	6	70	135–137(E)	79.2	6.1	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₃	79.5	6.0	3450(s)	1660	282	15300
	1.5	7	70	153–155(P)	76.3	6.1	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₄	75.8	5.7	3520(s)	1690	276	18700
Ar = Ar C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ p-	1.5	8	83	90–91 (E)	75.5	6.0	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₄	75.8	5.7	3400(br)	1660	280	16800
	1.5	9	66	106–107(E)	76.5	6.0	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₄	76.2	6.0	3430(s)	1660	276	15000
	3.5	10	71	118(M)	73.4	6.3	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₅	73.01	5.8	3530(s)	1670	276	18500

E = Ethanol, P = Light petroleum, M = Methanol.

TABLE 2

Ar(CO) ₂ Ar'*	Product	Yield %	M.p. °C	Found %			Formula	Required %			ν _{OH/cm}
				C	H	Cl		C	H	Cl	
Ar = Ar' = Ph	11	81	207–209(E)	85.8	6.6		C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₂	85.3	6.6		3570 (s.)
	12	73	184–185(E)	79.5	6.1		C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₄	78.9	6.1		3540
	13	73	169–170(E)	79.4	6.4		C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₄	78.9	6.1		3460 (s.)
Ar = Ph; Ar' = C ₆ H ₄ OMe(p-)	14	75	163–164(P)	81.6	6.2		C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₃	81.8	6.0		3500, 3570 (br.)
	15	66	172–174(P)	81.8	7.1		C ₂₉ H ₂₈ O ₃	82.1	6.6		3560 (s.)
	16	78	175–177(P)	77.0	6.0		C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₅	76.3	6.1		3500 (s.)
	17	78	165–167(P)	77.0	6.0		C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₅	76.3	6.1		3540
Ar = Ar' = C ₆ H ₄ OMe(p-)	18	79	228–230(E)	79.0	6.8		C ₃₀ H ₂₀ O ₄	79.3	6.6		3550–3400(br.)
	19	75	179–180(E)	73.9	6.2		C ₃₀ H ₂₀ O ₆	74.0	6.1		3500–3400(s.)
	20	73	165–167(E)	74.4	5.6		C ₃₀ H ₂₀ O ₆	74.0	6.1		3500(s.)
Ar = Ph; Ar' = C ₆ H ₄ Cl ₂ (p-)	21	71	153–155(M)	77.9	5.1	8.7	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ ClO ₂	77.9	5.2	8.9	3550(s.)
	22	75	169–170(P')	73.5	5.9	7.8	C ₂₈ H ₂₅ ClO ₄	72.9	5.4	7.7	3460, 3500
	23	75	148–150(M)	73.6	5.7	7.6	C ₂₈ H ₂₅ ClO ₄	72.9	5.4	7.7	3460, 3550
Ar = Ar' = C ₄ H ₄ O	24	69	114–116(P')	76.0	5.1		C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₄	76.3	5.2		3550(s.)
	25	64	128–130(M)	77.4	5.9		C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄	77.3	5.9		3750(s.)
	26	69	128–130(B)	71.6	5.8		C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₆	70.9	5.4		3450(s.)
	27	69	129–131(B)	70.4	5.3		C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₃	70.9	5.4		3550, 3450(s.)

B = Benzene; E = Ethanol; P = Benzene/light petroleum; P' = light petroleum; M = Methanol.
* Excess Grignard reagent = (6 moles).

References

1. R. ROGER and A. MCGREGOR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 442.
2. Cf. W. VAN E. DOERING and R. S. URBAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 5938.
3. E. S. GOULD. Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry, Holt Rinehart and Winston Inc., New York, 1964 (a) p. 636. (b) p. 550.
4. D. B. SHARP and E. L. MILLER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 5643.
5. L. J. BELLAMY, *Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules*, Methuen, London, 1961, p. 96.
6. J. E. LEFFLER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 1785.